

Carnival in Rio de Janeiro and lust: a designer's look

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Abstract:

It became a *cliché* to say that Carnival in Rio de Janeiro is “the greatest spectacle in the world”. Among several events that are held along three days – indeed, a longer period, for many city routines are affected, several days before – maybe the most known outside is the “Samba Schools Parade”. More than one hundred thousand people convene to enjoy *samba*, both to watch and to dance, and millions see by TV around the country and the world.

This paper aims to analyze a curious dichotomy, perceived through a critical look at the messy, glossy, breathtaking show. In one hand, almost naked bodies are the target of lust from spectators. On the other hand, people heavily overdressed exert the desire of being who they are not. The “carnival designers” face these authentic needs, aligning *desire* and *lust* among the concepts they usually deal with, to satisfy both categories of customers.

Conference theme: Desire & Lust

Keywords: desire, lust, carnival

Introduction

Carnival has different characteristics throughout the world. In this paper, we will exclusively look at Rio de Janeiro's Carnival, where there is a strong presence of lust and desire as nowhere else, we claim. It will be discussed how this relationship works, and how designers deal with it. We here refer to a significant contingent of design professionals that make their living on carnival, working for promoters of the big parade along the year.

The following session exposes our approach to the theme, and describes the method we used to collect and process data. In the sequence, a session brings some information about carnival, its origins, its profile in different places, and a more precise description of carnival in Rio. Then we introduce the core of our research: an attempt to correlate aspects of desire and lust in carnival to our history and particular aspects of our culture. Closing sessions expose our conclusions and present the references.

Methodology

What is desire? What is lust? Authoritative sources say:

Desire: "...-n. 1.A wish, longing, or craving." (American Heritage, 1970);

Lust: "...n 1 : sexual desire often to an intense or unrestrained degree." (Merriam-Webster, 1966).

We will stick to these particular meanings for the entries, to try to explore a peculiar aspect of carnival in Rio de Janeiro. To start up, we pose some questions:

- Where does the extreme and excessive style of Rio's carnival come from?
- Why so many people strive for an exposed spot in the parade? Why so many women pay to expose their bodies in such tiny costumes? On the other hand, why poor people from the samba school community dream on wearing heavy and hot costumes related to nobility? How can we explain this antithesis?

We are looking for answers for the preceding questions. It seems obvious that feelings of desire and lust are involved, associated to the very ancestral cultural heritage of carnival feast. A brief exercise on etymology points to *caro*, flesh (Araújo, 1999), then associates intrinsically Carnival, in its origin, to lust, sexual desire, loosening of behavior rules.

A broader investigation on related bibliography resulted unfruitful, in terms of quantitative analyses on this matter. So, the adopted approach was to carry out a simple documental and iconographic survey, mainly based on material available in the media. The lines presented here were transcribed from prestigious and internationally known newspapers from Brazil, freely translated by authors. The usage of such lines is to illustrate and helps the discussion of the

main theme. Some pictures, also transcribed from media, are eloquent for themselves, and support assertions here presented.

This study was based on the experience of the authors' knowledge, whether working as designer in a samba school entity or dealing with this theme in a number of academic works, besides their personal lifelong involvement, since both were born and live in Rio.

The Stuff the Dreams are Made on: What is Rio de Janeiro's Carnival Made on?

The Carnival Party

Carnival happens in February or March, according to modern western calendar. It is a movable celebration, ruled by old ephemerides, and is set for forty days before Easter. There are many theories about this cultural manifestation that we call "carnival", but most of them quote this short time as a period for liberation that precedes Lent, the period for penitence (Araújo, 1999). Nowadays, while in New Orleans happens the biggest carnival in North America, the *Mardi Gras* or Fat Tuesday, with people in very strange costumes all over the streets, and in Venice, the traditional masquerades fill the Saint Mark's Square, in Rio de Janeiro the main event is the Samba School's Parade.

Let's not digress on the details of all the transformations of this manifestation through the centuries and throughout the world; instead, we will focus on carnival in Rio de Janeiro, from around 1920, where the reports set the birth of the first *Escolas de Samba*, herein referred to as Samba Schools. Previously, for each social layer there was a carnival group, a particular form to play. The high society, born in the second half of the XIX century, paraded with social critics plots, presented in the sound of operas, with luxurious costumes and cars; these events were organized by the richest layers of the society, organized in *Sociedades Carnavalescas* (Cavalcanti, 2006). Another kind of association, the *Ranchos*, originated by the end of the XIX century also paraded with a plot, costumes and cars, in the sound of its particular march, and were organized by the bourgeoisie. The *Blocos*, a small structured form of group, were formed by the poorest groups of the society, the slum people. The first Samba Schools came to mess up this social stratification, and to flatten differences. The social cores of the schools were the *blocos*, so it was a somehow daring attitude, for a well-born representative of society, to belong to a Samba School at that time. The first samba school, in the early 20's, was named *Deixa Falar*, a colloquial expression that stands for "Let Them Gossip" (Moraes, 1987).

Shifting to present days, we see a much evolved scenario. From some years now, the parade lasts all night long, along two days, when the 12 most famous samba schools show up. Huge decorated carts (mounted on the biggest trucks frames), cohorts of participants richly dressed according to the chosen theme, and the roaring *bateria* (percussion band) march and dance

along a gigantic catwalk, between spectators from all the world, in a modern concrete structure specially built for this purpose.

Design, Designers and Carnival

What has this to do with design and designers? Well, the simplest answer points to the fact that, behind each school preparation for the parade, there is one year of serious work for more than 500 people. Many of them are designers, as well as other professionals, all involved in the production of the gigantic carts, decorating elements and luxurious costumes. It's like the production of a big opera exhibition, complicated by the fact that it involves people and vehicles in motion, and is played at open air (sometimes under heavy summer tropical rain!). But a more elusive aspect of involvement of the design thinking and feeling in this enterprise refers to desire and lust. Once again, there is a first obvious clue: this event is seen worldwide as an exposure of naked bodies, target of lust from people who want to elicit desires. Nevertheless, we claim that there is another strong aspect of exertion of desire and lust, maybe unexpected at a first glance, behind the outer layer of glamour.

Desire and Lust: Dressing, Undressing, Overdressing

The exuberant dancers, a common characteristic of the parades, excite the public libido, especially foreign tourists, attracted by this curious fact. The parade images shown by TV all around the world are focused in the nudity of beautiful women, transmitting maybe the idea that it is something common through all the year, and that all those women sell their bodies. It is well known that a contingent of tourists look for "sexual tourism", and carnival in Rio is one of their preferred destinations (Gripp, A.; Bottari, 2004).

Nevertheless, a great spectacle like this one is not all about beautiful women half naked. Each school comes to the parade with about 4,000 components, and most of them live in the school's community ("community" is the politically correct synonym for *favela*, the slum). As reported before, the samba schools were created in the poorest regions of Rio de Janeiro, having been greatly influenced by negro descendants of former African slaves. Much of this culture is still used in the carnival, like musical instruments, dances, songs and garment of deities of ancestral African religions and myths. Anyway, over the time some characters became more and more elaborated. There are roles of kings and queens in every school, and they are deeply wanted by the community members. Other roles, like nobles, sages and mythological entities abound, and their dresses use to be luxurious, shiny and impressive. So, the ones who wear those dresses leave the poverty back at least for one single day and have their dreams come true, by intensely living those *personae*!

The desire expressed by the willingness to wear a luxurious costume, play a important role in the parade and be the target of attention around the world is similar to one of the three desire classifications done by Desmet (2002), the one he calls "being it", which means "a desire for being or having some identified characteristic or quality".

A brief anthropological attempt to provide support for the precedent assertions

Ancient Influences

Brazilian people is originated basically by the union of the of native indians, africans brought as slaves and Portuguese conquerors. Our culture had a strong influence from each of these groups. We propose herein a way to make a correspondence between traces of these three origins and aspects of present carnival structure, as follows:

a - From the Brazilian Native Indians we got the Feathers and the Naked Bodies

Brazil was a country colonized by Portugal, “discovered” in 1500. The native were indians who shocked the Portuguese sailormen with their freedom and natural way of dealing their own nudity. They walked almost or totally naked, very different of the portuguese culture.

Besides the little clothing, the indians have the culture to adorn their own bodies with painting, seeds, vegetables, pieces of wood and feather. Indeed, like in some other cultures, plumery art was well developed among first native Brazilians, as it proceeds being practiced among the last representatives, mainly at Amazon region (Proença, 2003). These are some of the characteristics we inherited from the indian costumes, and a clue to explain the cultural manifestation of carnival: to wear feathers as a synonym of beauty and luxury, and to show nudity with all this, in a “natural” way. Examples of carnival costumes richly adorned by feathers, or plumes, and not much more, abound. Figure 1 shows a Brazilian model, who won Miss Brasil contest in 2007 and performed *Rainha da Bateria* (“Queen of Drums”) at prestigious Vila Isabel Samba School this year.

Figure 1: Natália Guimarães, Miss Brasil 2007 and “Queen of Drums” in 2008 (Gonzalez, 2008)

Figure 2 presents an extreme example. Viviane Castro, also model, parades wearing plumes, bijoux and literally nothing more! She was criticized by some segments of society, through media, for her daring and shameless attitude, but this is not a unique case, although uncommon.

Figure 2: Viviane Castro, Brazilian model, parades in her carnival dresses (Paiva, 05-feb-2008)

b - From the Africans we got the Rhythms and the Dance

When the Portuguese colonizers established in Brazil, they realized they needed labor force to help the exploitation and occupation of the land. As the indians proved to be incapable for the required jobs (for they refused conscription, and made war when forced), colonizers brought africans to work as slaves (Freyre, 1992). We are herein not dealing on issues concerning slavery, but only the culture and costumes aggregated to our own.

The african-brazilian cultural origins of samba and the miscegenation that generated the mulatto people of the urban poor layer, are points strongly affirmed in the literature. (Cavalcanti, 2006).

The beat that rocks the parade is *Samba*, by product of african rhythms. Samba players use instruments – different types of drums and other percussive devices – of african origin. The term "Samba" is also of african origin and is related to tribal dances. This rhythm comes with its own steps that becomes what is called *samba no pé* (“samba on the feet dance”), also learned from the earlier arrived africans and their descendants (Lopes, 2003).

Figure 3 shows an african-brazilian drummer, playing a typical samba’s instrument.

Figure 3: African-brazilian drummer, from the School’s community (Pawlowski, 2008)

c - The Portuguese Royal Family Brought Luxury, Opulence and the Baroque Art Style

Exactly 200 years ago, the Portuguese royal family disembarked in Brazil, escaping from Napoleon and war. This episode landed around 15 thousand people in Rio de Janeiro, with way of life and culture totally different than those of who lived here. The city became the new capital of the Portuguese kingdom; its citizens began to live among people showing jewels, silvery, silks, cloaks (Silva, 1992).

King, Queen, princes, nobles, unknown before, were all of a sudden incorporated in our day life. Segments from the rural aristocracy and from the rich middle class, avid to show importance and status, moved to Rio. The luxury and the pomp started to become common behavior amid the richest layers of the society, which begin to live in small castles and cover up

in jewelry. The local art suffered strong influence of the baroque art style, represented by the extravagant elements of gold, silver and gems brought by the royal family. (Etzel, 1974). Figure 4 shows typical allegoric items from the Samba School Parade, with all the luxury and opulence peculiar of the baroque art style.

Figure 4: Beija Flor's Spectacle, Champion Samba School of 2008 (Gonzalez, 2008)

In this arena, the lower layers – creators of the Samba – dreamed with access to royalty world, as if in a fairy tale. That is where the influence of that particular period comes to play in the scenarios and costumes of the samba schools parades. The composition of a samba school parade (in terms of aesthetic approach to the theme, sequence and disposition of characters, decorated cars, percussion band, etc) passes under permanent change, but one aspect remains untouched: the main dancers, *Mestre Sala* and *Porta Bandeira*, who bear the revered school flag, proceed parading richly dressed as nobles, representatives of high aristocracy. Figure 5 shows the couple of *Mestre Sala* and *Porta Bandeira* who performed these roles along about 38 years at Imperatriz Leopoldinense Samba School.

Figure 5: Chiquinho, *Mestre Sala* and Maria Helena, *Porta Bandeira* (Imperatriz Leopoldinense, 2005)

Another Relevant Variable: Summer, the Hottest Season

Brazilian carnival happens in a variable date between February and March, when it is summer in the southern hemisphere. Rio de Janeiro is one of the hottest cities in Brazil, where temperatures reach around 35°C or even 40°C. Because of these high temperatures and the beach environment, people are used to wear light and scarce clothes, and the worship of the body is marked. Thus, body exposure does not necessarily bear sex appeal as it seems; depending on circumstances, it just reflects our free way of dressing, especially because climate and culture.

Consequences: getting a role at the parade

Most components of a Samba School come from its own community and are usually very poor. These people fancy on wearing a noble costume, heavy, luxurious and flamboyant, as the Portuguese nobility and royalty used to wear. Some of these costumes weight more than 30 kg and are extremely hot. They are awkward even to walk, not to say to perform acrobatic dance! The luxury, by the way, was slowly incorporated in the parade's elements. In the 70's Joãozinho Trinta, considered as one of the greatest carnival artists of all times, revolutionized the parades following the baroque art style in the details and exploring the splendor of the elements. He often justified his ways simply by his now famous quotation: "Poor people like luxury". We can trace a parallel between this statement and Jordan's comment (2000) about status:

"Many products can have a role as 'social accessories' - helping to generate or maintain a particular image. People may want to own or use products whose design tallies with their image of themselves – how they think others see them, or how they would wish others to see them". Therefore, the costumes and decorating elements bring emotional aspects that satisfy both status and wealth desires of the components, at least for a few hours.

Besides the clothing, the monarchy influence also reflects in the roles within the parade. Kings and Queens are very common characters, sometimes with different features. There is a role of Queen of the Drums, for instance, that is the most disputed. For decades, the most beautiful woman of the community used to be nominated for this role, since she was presumably the one who should better represent it. It is expected from the Queen of the Drums, as she parades ahead the percussion band, to dance samba with grace and perfect style, and this ability was naturally expected from someone living at the community. Today this role is almost always occupied by some model or actress, who, most of the times, pay for the costume. The already mentioned costume that, although very luxurious, cover almost nothing of the body! It happens that sometimes that beautiful model or actress is not proficient as samba dancer, has no *samba no pé*, and such argument is source of interminable quarreling at TV talk shows, newspapers and magazines after every carnival!

Figure 6: Maria Helena e Chiquinho, without the carnival costumes.("O Batuque", 2006)

On the other hand, there is genuine commitment from community members to play at the parade, and they are proud of their roles. Picture shown in Figure 6 was taken during a ceremony to award prominent carnival players and dancers. The couple here depicted is the same who perform their dance in Figure 5. They are indeed mother and son, and she, a poor

resident of the community, was being honored as a personality at her samba school, where she had performed, for years, as *Porta Bandeira*.

Behind the Show: Designers and Others

From millions of viewers who watch Rio's carnival live or on TV, only a few know about the work involved, till the spectacle finally happens. Each one of the "Special Group" samba schools starts its works around 10 months before the parade. It is common to finish a parade already planning the next one. About 400 people, sometimes 500 or more, work for each school, and among them there are many designers, stylists, scenery makers and fine artists. For a good parade to happen, it's necessary that every single aspect work properly and the school be able to touch and excite the audience. This empathy with the public is unpredictable, it happens – or not – at the moment of the parade, if it is capable to charm the audience.

The basic schedule of preparation of a parade through the previous year is as follows: choose of a theme, which involves the presentation, elaboration of the samba which will be sung during the presentation, creation and confection of the allegoric scenery parts, adornments and costumes, many rehearsals and, finally, the show.

Inside the building where the allegoric items are made, there is this feeling of unit and a great will to make a wonderful spectacle and win the contest. Almost all the carnival workers participate of the parade, their commitment and integration are visible, and they strive to guarantee the so wanted title.

Sometimes we can observe a kind of prejudice between some designers, which consider the carnival minor art. In Brazil it is still common this sense that a product should always have a function. However, Norman (2004) highlights the importance of the product's utility and usability, but stresses that "without fun, pleasure, joy, excitement [...] our lives would be incomplete". And Löbach (2000) says that the satisfaction of aesthetic needs is not essential for our physical existence, but to our mental health.

Moreover, it is observed that the Samba Schools with the best results in the parade have creation and production processes well structured, similar to those applied by industrial designers. In these Schools, the traditionally handiwork is replaced by a production line with planning, division of tasks and quality control. The command of the activities is not only at hands of a *carnavalesco*, but a team. To compose this team, designers have the ideal profile.

Conclusion

Even sometimes neglected by some Brazilian designers, Carnival brings serious design issues in Rio de Janeiro. On the conceptual field, it is an opportunity to exert our profession within a very rich environment, dealing with aspects much more intricate than the ones dealt with in current literature, mainly taking into account that the most respected authors in Design matters live or lived in countries and cultures where carnival plays a minor role. On the professional field, it is remarkable that dozens of designers make their living on jobs related to carnival, thus generating more jobs for hundreds of other professionals, just by working for the success of the Samba School Parade.

In the precedent text we tried to explore one peculiar aspect of carnival in Rio: desire and lust abound at the parade, both in spectators and players. Findings of our research, mainly based on material from the media and testimonies personally taken from people involved in the parade seem to support the central statement of this paper, which constitutes a curious dichotomy: at the parade, beautiful women get almost undressed, thus provoking viewers and eliciting lust; at the same time, persons who normally wear simply and modestly overdress with luxury garments, to realize a fancy of being rich and noble.

Authors of this paper intend just to launch these questions, pretending to be dealing with issues centrally focused at a more comprehensive theme, “Emotion in Design”, exploring the emotional aspects that surround the parades, making an analogy between these aspects and some emotional design concepts, and maybe motivating their peers from other places, where carnival is seen from different points of view, to enlarge and enrich the discussion.

References

- American Heritage (1970). “Dictionary of the English Language.” Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Araújo, H. (1999). “Carnaval, seis milênios de história.” Griphus.
- Cavalcanti, M.L.V.C. (2006). “Tempo Ritual: O Desfile das Escolas de Samba no Rio de Janeiro.” *Terceira Margem*, 27-39.
- Desmet, P. M.A. (2002). “Designing emotions.” PhD Thesis, Delft University of Technology.
- Etzel, E. (1974). “O Barroco no Brasil: Psicologia e Remanescentes.” *Melhoramentos*.
- Freyre, G. (1992). “Casa-grande e Senzala.” *Record*.
- Gonzalez, I. (2008). “Musas do carnaval”. *O Globo Online Newspaper*, 05-feb-2008. Available: <<http://oglobo.globo.com/carnaval2008/rio/default.asp>>. Accessed in 11-may-2008.
- Gripp, A.; Bottari, E. (2004). “Turistas em busca do prazer.” *O Globo Newspaper*, Rio de Janeiro, 15-feb-2004.
- Imperatriz Leopoldinense (2005). “Fotos da Imperatriz Leopoldinense 2005” Available: <<http://imperatriz.free.fr/album3/2005/fotos2005.php>>. Accessed in 15-may-2008.
- Jordan, P. W. (2000). “Designing pleasurable products. An introduction to the new human factors”. Taylor & Francis.

- Löbach, B. (2000). "Design Industrial: bases para a configuração dos produtos industriais". Edgard Blücher.
- Lopes, N. (2003). "Sambeabá." Casa da Palavra.
- Merriam-Webster (2002). "Concise Dictionary of English Usage."
- Moraes, E. (1987) "História do carnaval carioca." Record.
- Norman, D. (2004). "Emotional design. Why we love or hate everyday things." Basic Books.
- O Batuque (2006). "Destaques do Carnaval 2006." Available:
<http://www.obatuque.com/obatuque/destaques_carnaval_2006/20060627_destiques_do_carnaval_2006.htm>. Accessed in 15-may-2008 .
- Paiva, G. (2008). "Musas do carnaval". O Globo Online Newspaper, 05-feb-2008. Available:
<<http://oglobo.globo.com/carnaval2008/rio/default.asp>>. Accessed in 11-may-2008.
- Pawlowski, B. (2008). "Carnaval 2008." Available:
<<http://www.brianpawlowski.com/Carnaval2008>>. Accessed in 30-apr-2008.
- Proença, G. (2003). "História da Arte." Ática.
- Silva, F.A. (1992). "História do Brasil." Moderna.